

FOSTERING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS FOR A SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE
INTENSIVE INDUSTRY ACROSS THE EXTENDED CONSTRUCTION VALUE CHAIN

Report on stakeholders' Network setting up

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D1.1: Stakeholders' network setting up

WP 1, T 1.1

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

0. Summary

The aim of this task is to establish a network of stakeholders that may be interested in FISSAC model to foster future replicability in other countries and regions. This report summarises the first exercise of identification and mapping of relevant stakeholders across the construction value chain (industry, Industrial Symbiosis consultancies, policy makers, public authorities, research institutes, civic society organisations and others).

At this initial stage, the purpose is to form a broad network of stakeholders that can be later filtered and sorted by category of interest. The list of contacts will be used for future communication (newsletters, conferences and other project dissemination and capacity building activities).

All project partners were requested to submit their input and indicate a list of actors with whom have regular collaboration, and that would be interested in the FISSAC project activities.

A total of one thousand and five hundred direct contacts were compiled and more than nine hundred actors were overall identified, either as 'warm contacts' or contacts of indirect interest in the FISSAC project. The majority of identified actors comes from the industry (materials producers, managers, federations, construction) followed by research and innovation organisations, public authorities and consultancies.

The stakeholders' network will continue to be updated with new recommended contacts throughout the project lifetime (2015-2020).

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Abbreviations and acronyms

1. Introduction

1.1 The project

The European- funded project FISSAC 'Fostering Industrial Symbiosis for a Sustainable resource intensive industry Across the value Chain' aims at developing and demonstrating a new paradigm built on an innovative industrial symbiosis model towards a zero waste approach in the resource intensive industries of the construction value chain, tackling harmonized technological and non-technological requirements, leading to material closed- loop processes and moving to a circular economy. The project kicked off in September 2015 and will last until February 2020.

FISSAC project is run by a diverse consortium of twenty-six partners from nine countries (eight EU Member States and Turkey) ranging from: general contractor and engineering construction companies, non-profit research organisations, SMEs in different sustainable business fields, a public authority, intensive industries, an association for standardisation and certification and an international association of local and regional authorities promoting recycling and sustainable resource management.

1.2 Objective

One of the first tasks of FISSAC project was to conduct a stakeholder analysis which aimed to identify early enough those stakeholders that would provide a holistic overview of all technical and non-technical aspects pertaining to Industrial Symbiosis and circular economy. These actors may also be interested in the FISSAC model to foster future replicability in other countries and regions. Setting an accurate stakeholders' network will therefore allow for:

- Engaging with interested stakeholders on a regular basis
- Gaining insight from experts' views
- Assisting with communication and dissemination activities
- Ensuring an optimal outreach of project deliverables
- Maximising the impact of project deliverables

2. Analysis

All project partners were requested to contribute to this exercise and submit their recommended companies and actors in the FISSAC stakeholder network. ACR+ was the point of contact for collecting the information and compiling it into a consolidated file.

The relevant actors and contacts were assigned into various groups of interests which were then prioritised by relevance and interest to the project topics ('priority 1' and 'priority 2').²

Figure 1 – Planning of stakeholder analysis

2.1 Results

2.1.1 Actors

The majority of identified as directly 'interested actors'- priority 1 are the industry contacts- materials producers and managers (153), followed by industry federations representatives (82), and Research and Innovation groups (58). Public authorities (51) are also well represented in the network, as well as consultancies (38) and industry- construction companies (30). The network is completed by civil society organisations and associations, media, European and international organisations, industry- architects, industry property management, policy makers, industry federations and technology providers (see Figure 2).

² Please note that we would define as Priority 1 companies or entities who are actively involved in the construction value chain and would be directly interested in FISSAC activities. Priority 2 would be less relevant actors, namely secondary stakeholders who would be indirectly involved in the project.

Figure 2 – Type of actors-priority 1

Out of a total of four hundred and ten 'priority 2 actors' overall identified, the majority come from public authorities (119), followed by Industry- materials producers and managers (51), consultancies (50), Research and Innovation groups (46), civil society organisations and associations (37) and industry-construction (31) and architects (27) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Type of actors-priority 2

The majority of directly interested contacts are active in the following countries: Spain, Sweden and Turkey followed by Belgium, the United Kingdom and Czech Republic, not surprisingly as a number of FISSAC partners are active in these countries.

Figure 4 – Countries with high representation

2.1.2 Contacts

Looking at the directly interested contacts compiled, the majority come from the industry- materials producer/ manager, then public authorities, industry federations, research and innovation organisations and consultancies. Civil society groups and associations, industry- construction, European and international organisations, industry- architect and property management are also well represented.

Figure 5 – Type of direct contacts- priority 1

Finally, out of one thousand and five hundred identified contacts in the FISSAC stakeholders' network, the wide majority comes from public authorities (41%), which can be explained thanks to the contribution from ACR+ network of members. The second biggest target group is Research and Innovation groups (18%), followed by industry- materials producers and managers (10%), consultancies (8%), industry federations (8%), civil society organisations (6%) and industry- construction (3%).

Figure 6 – Contacts TOTAL

3. Follow- up

The present analysis will help with future dissemination of project deliverables, in particular the innovative industrial symbiosis model and the software platform. The stakeholders are expected to be involved at different stages of the FISSAC project (e.g. participate in Living Labs and webinars; provide insight in the Social strategies and engagement work; replicate FISSAC model in new markets and regions). The multi-stakeholder approach will allow for better implementation of the project findings; depending on the activity partners may focus on specific categories of actors for targeted dissemination or exchange of best practice (e.g. industry best practice for Industrial Symbiosis).

With regards to the number of stakeholders and the fair representation in the network, the project partners will focus their efforts on identifying additional contacts in those countries with lower turnout (see Figure 4) where the FISSAC project is represented (i.e. Germany, Italy and Hungary). The project partners will also target future stakeholders in less-represented professional categories (i.e. civil society organisations and associations, industry federations, industry- constructions, architects and media) which will get involved in various phases of the project. A special feature will be prepared to encourage professionals getting involved and collect additional contacts directly from the FISSAC website.

Important to note is that personal data from stakeholders will be used internally in the Consortium. Future management of collected data (email addresses, phone numbers, etc.) will follow the guidelines and management of Ethics issues set in the Grant Agreement.

4. Conclusion

The first step of establishing networks of relevant stakeholders who will share their insight on best practices, participate actively in workshops and webinars and contribute to Industrial Symbiosis (IS) experiences is now completed. This exercise follows a multi-stakeholder approach covering from industries and IS consultancies to researchers, civil society organisations and public authorities who are the main target audiences of FISSAC project.

